

VARIETAL RESPONSE OF IRISH POTATOES TO IRRIGATION SCHEDULING IN THE
NORTHERN GUINEA SAVANNAH ZONE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The effects of cumulative pan evaporation (CPE)-based irrigation scheduling on growth, yield, crop water use and crop water use efficiency of Irish potatoes (*Solannum tuberosum L.*) were studied. Irrigation scheduling was at CPE of 20 mm, 30 mm, 40 mm and irrigating at 7-days rotation (Control). Net depth of 50 mm was used. Pakistan, Nicola, SP and Dual were the four varieties of Irish potatoes used for the study. Irrigating at 20 mm resulted in early flowering, early germination, highest total yield at harvest, largest tuber sizes, heaviest tubers, and largest total number of tubers. Seasonal crop water use and crop water use efficiency were found to be 551 mm and 48.85 X10⁻³. Dual exhibited best performance in terms of early germination, total number of tubers and tuber weights; but the largest tuber sizes were produced by variety Pakistan. The 7-day rotational irrigation which is the conventional irrigation interval for the crop in this region did not turn to favor the growth and yield of the crop. Irrigation interval of not more than four days is therefore recommended for the growth and production of the crop in this region when a net depth of 50 mm is used on a loamy soil.

KEY WORDS: Irrigation, scheduling, potatoes, northern guinea savannah, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Irish potato, is a food as well as a cash crop introduced in to Nigeria by the Europeans in the 1920s (Roger et al., 2002) and has high economic value (Horton and Fano, 1984). Formal research on the growth and production of the crop in Nigeria dates to 1940, but still it is not a staple food in the nation (Obigbesan, 1976; Ifenkwe, 1978; Rhoades et al., 2002). This is attributed to the harsh weather conditions of the arid and semi-arid ecological regions (Manrique, 1993; Ogunwale and Owonubi, 1998; Okai et al., 2002) to which two-thirds of Nigeria's total land belong (FAO-AGL, 2002). Potato irrigation in the northern guinea savannah has a long history, but the farmers generally lack the basic knowledge of crop water requirement irrigation skill. There is a dwindling availability of water for irrigation in the region. As a result, water application had been haphazard with no specific irrigation interval. This could result in over- or under-irrigation both of which could translate to wastage of the limited water resources, flood, soil salinization, yield depression, and, hence, farmers' economic distress (James, 1988; Sharma and Dixit, 1992; Frank et al., 1994; Mouromical and Ierna, 1995; Shock, 2002). Doorenbos and Kassam (1981), also stated that over irrigation, especially during the flowering, leads to flower drops and poor yields, but many farmers do misinterpret this sign to mean crop water stress and they add water again, worsening the negative consequence of over irrigation. Potato has low tolerance for both water stress and water logging (CSIDC, 2001; Shock, 2002).

Irrigation scheduling, a technique that determines the amount and frequency of water application, plays an important role in managing limited water resources. It can arrest crop water stress, improve yield, and ensure efficient use of energy and production cost and it is environmentally friendly. Correct timing of irrigation application is of overriding importance, since delayed irrigation, particularly when the crop is sensitive to water stress, could seriously affect yields which cannot be compensated by subsequent over watering (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1984). Information on irrigation scheduling of Irish potatoes in Northern Nigeria is lacking. This work examined the effect of irrigation scheduling on growth, yield, and water use efficiency of some varieties of Irish potatoes in a tropical, semi-arid environment. The study specifically determined the optimum moisture required for potato growth and production, developed an operational irrigation schedule for Irish potato, and assessed the effect of irrigation scheduling on yield, crop water use, and crop water use efficiency of four varieties of Irish potatoes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was conducted during the cool-dry season, October, 2003 through April, 2004 at the Irrigation Research Farm of the Institute for Agricultural Research, Samaru-Zaria (11°1'N, 7°38'E, 686 m above sea level) in the semi-arid zone of the northern guinea savannah, Nigeria. The mean monthly maximum and minimum air temperatures for this season were 32.6°C and 16.7°C, respectively. No rainfall was recorded. The soil moisture content at field capacity (-0.03 bar) and wilting point (15 bars) were 19.86 g g⁻¹ and 4.96 g g⁻¹, respectively. The soil of the study site was loamy in texture, slightly acidic in reaction with low organic matter, total nitrogen, and exchangeable cations. It is also poor in magnesium, potassium and sodium (Table 1).

The experimental design was a factorial combination of irrigation schedules and varieties of Irish potatoes (4²) laid in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Each replication was separated from another by two buffer ridges and a ridge to separate two adjacent plots. The four levels of irrigation were at cumulative pan evaporation (CPE) of 20 mm, 30 mm, 40 mm and a fixed interval of 7 days (the control). These values corresponded to cumulative pan evaporation/ irrigation (CPE/IR) of 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 respectively. Pan evaporation method is one of the FAO-recommended methods of estimating crop water use, since it provides a measure of the integrated effect of radiation, wind, temperature and humidity on open water body and plants respond to the variables in the same fashion (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1984; Smith and Kassam, 2001). The four varieties of potato used were Pakistan, Nicola, SP, and Dual. Each treatment had resulted in to net depth of application of 50 mm. Each of the treatments was randomly assigned to a plot. The furrow irrigation method was used, with furrows spaced 0.75 m apart. Each plot was 2.25 m X 10 m and a total of 48 plots were used. Compound fertilizer (25N:10P:10K) was used at the rate of 100 kg N, 90 kg P and 80 kg K per hectare. Fifty percent of the doses were applied basally and worked into the soil during harrowing. The remaining 50 % was applied as side dressing four weeks after planting. The potato variety seeds were planted on sides of the ridges 30 cm apart. Daily evaporation from a class "A" pan was collected at the Samaru weather station and added cumulatively until any of the three CPE values selected was reached. This was used to trigger the irrigation of plots to which the three CPE values were assigned. Plots to which 7 days were assigned were irrigated every 7 days. The plots were weeded three times during the growing season. A heavy first irrigation was applied to all plots.

A 100 mm cutthroat metal flume was used to measure the amount of water diverted into each plot at per irrigation to arrive at the seasonal volume of water used. Soil moisture content was determined at least 24 hrs before and after every irrigation to arrive at the estimate of the soil moisture depletion from which consumptive use by the plants was computed. A 100 mm diameter galvanized access tube was located at the center of each plot to a depth of 1 m with which a neutron probe (CPN model) was used. Twelve tensiometers (four per replication) were placed some 30 cm below the soil surface and read daily at 4:00 p.m to observe at what soil suction any of the selected values would be reached.

The numbers of days to 50 % germination, 50 % flowering and 50 % tuberisation, which are major growth parameters of Irish potatoes, were monitored. Yield components observed included total yield at harvest, tuber size and distribution, total number of tubers and mean tuber weights. The crop water use efficiency was determined from the crop water use and total yield at harvest as provided by Michael (1988). All relevant data relating to crop yields and irrigation parameters were subjected to statistical analysis of variance using the F- test as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1967). Differences among the treatment means and their interactions were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Days to 50 % Germination, Flowering and Tuberisation.

The growth components were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by varieties. Variety SP attained 50 % germination, flowering and tuberisation at 24, 70 and 50 days, respectively. These results were attributed to variations in the genetic potential among the varieties studied (Table 2). Two of the varieties (Nicola and Dual) were observed to be non-flowering varieties. There were no statistical differences among irrigation scheduling treatments with days to 50 % tuberisation. Days to 50 % germination and flowering, respectively, were unaffected by irrigation scheduling, as the scheduling were imposed after germination and flowering had started. Doorenbos and Kassam (1981) pointed out that the moisture required for crop germination is far below the full potential evaporation.

Total Yields at Harvest.

Variety Dual yielded the highest. It was followed by Nicola, Pakistan, and SP in that orders (Table 2). All the varieties were, however, statistically at par in terms of total yields. Irrigation scheduling did not significantly ($P < 0.05$) influence yield at harvest. However, irrigating at cumulative pan evaporation (CPE) of 20 mm resulted in higher yield than the other scheduling treatments. Increasing the CPE value by a step of 10 mm up to 40 mm did not translate to a yield increase. Irrigation at 7-days rotation resulted in a 40 % yield depression when compared to the yield obtained at CPE of 20 mm (Table 2). Similar results were observed by Gregory and Simmonds (1992) and Mouromical and Ierna (1995) who reported that an increase in water influenced the photosynthetic activities of the plants. This, in turn, directly translates into a decrease in yield and yield components. The interactions of varieties with irrigation schedule revealed that Dual with CPE of 20 mm produced the highest yield, while irrigating Pakistan at CPE of 30 mm yielded the least.

Tuber Sizes

There was a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among varieties with respect to size grading. Largest tubers (tubers greater than or equal to 76.2 mm but less than 101.6 mm in diameter) were produced by variety Pakistan (Table 2). The numerical values of Nicola, SP, and Dual in this size range were statistically at par. Dual, however, had the smallest of this size range. There was no statistical difference among irrigation scheduling treatments with respect to this size range. Irrigating at CPE 20 mm resulted in the highest yield. The fixed 7-days irrigation resulted in the poorest sizes with a 207 % size reduction compared to that from CPE 20 mm. The other size ranges ($T < 25.4$ mm, $25.4 \text{ mm} > T \geq 25.4$ mm, and $50.8 > T \geq 76.2$ mm) followed exactly similar patters both with varietal and irrigation scheduling treatments. The interactions of varieties with irrigation schedules revealed that irrigating Pakistan at CPE 20 mm produced the largest tuber sizes, while variety SP at CPE 30 mm produced the smallest tuber sizes. These results are in conformity with the observations of Sharma and Dixit (1992) and Roger, et al. (2002).

Number of Tubers

There was no statistical difference both among varieties and irrigation scheduling treatments with respect to total number of tubers. Dual, however, showed the highest numerical value of number of tubers. This was followed by SP, Nicola, and Pakistan in that order. Pakistan, the variety that produced the highest yields with the largest tuber sizes, had a low number of tubers. The fixed 7 day irrigation produced the least number of tubers when compared to those obtained when others were irrigated at CPE 20 mm, 30 mm and 40 mm (Table 2).

Mean Tuber Weight

Both irrigation and varietal treatments did not significantly affect the mean tuber weight, but a closer look at the results showed that variety Dual produced heaviest tubers. This was followed closely by Nicola and Pakistan. Variety SP produced the lightest tubers that were 40% lighter than Dual. This result may be attributed to genotypic differences in tolerance to the production environment. Benoit et al. (1983) and Shock (2002) reported similar observations among various potato varieties. The mean tuber weights responded in a reciprocal fashion to CPE values. Irrigating at CPE 40 mm resulted in very light tubers, while plots irrigated at CPE 20 mm were found to have the heaviest tubers. The fixed 7-day irrigation resulted in the lightest tubers. This was because plots irrigated at a 7-days interval were relatively drier, thus those plants had suffered a short fall of available water relative to the plants' transpiration rate. This usually negates proper photosynthetic, process which, in turn, results in reduced leaf area, cell size, and general morphology of the plants and; hence, reduction of dry matter accumulation in the tubers. Similar observations have been reported by other authors (Manrique, 1993; Lynch et al., 1995 and Mourimical and Ierna, 1995). The interaction of irrigation with varieties revealed that irrigating Dual at CPE 20 mm produced the heaviest tubers (47.67 g) which was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than all other combinations. Variety SP irrigated with a CPE of 20 mm resulted in the lightest tubers.

Irrigation variables

Parameters observed were irrigation events, seasonal depth of water, irrigation interval and seasonal volume of water. More irrigation events, larger seasonal depth of water, shorter irrigation intervals and larger seasonal volumes of water were used in plots irrigated at CPE 20 mm. This occurred as a result of high temperatures, fast wind speeds and low humidity during the dry seasons. The numerical values of these parameters were least with the fixed 7-day irrigation as indicated in Table 3.

Crop Water Use (CWU) and Crop Water Use Efficiency (CWUE)

The numerical values of crop water use and crop water use efficiency of all the varieties were statistically at par. However, the variety SP used up the largest amount of water and consequently, had the poorest water use efficiency. Pakistan, the variety that produced the largest tuber sizes exhibited the best water use efficiency compared to the other varieties. Irrigation schedules affected CWU and CWUE. Irrigating at CPE 20 mm had the highest seasonal crop water use. But increasing the CPE value by a step of 10 mm up to CPE 40 mm resulted in reduction of CWU. The fixed 7-day irrigation resulted in the least water use. Doorenbos and Kassam (1981) had earlier reported that the seasonal Potato evapotranspiration ranged from 300-800 mm for different climatic and environmental conditions. Similar patterns were observed with CWUE in which irrigating at CPE 20 mm proved to be the most economic in water utilization despite the high irrigation frequency and large seasonal water use (Table 3). CPE 20 mm was the level at which the best performance was observed in terms of total yield, largest tuber sizes, a total number of tubers, and tuber weights. These results generally concord with earlier findings (Feibert and Shock, 2000; Mofoke, et al., 2003)

CONCLUSION

Best yields of Irish potatoes on sandy loamy soil were obtained when irrigated at CPE 20-40 mm at 50 mm net depth. This corresponded to a 4 day irrigation interval. The 7 day rotational irrigation that is conventionally practiced in the area yielded comparatively low. While variety Pakistan produced the largest tuber sizes, variety Dual proved to be the most profitable when emphasis is placed on early germination, early tuberisation, a large number of tubers, heavy tubers, and water use efficiency.

The optimum moisture for potato growth and production is a factor of climate, soil and variety. The seasonal moisture requirement was found to range between 341.2 mm to 551 mm. The results of this study could be used in modeling to simulate a longer irrigation interval in many countries, especially in West Africa. This research relied on climatic parameters and many countries across West Africa from Senegal to Tanzania are all on the same climatic axis with northern Nigeria having similar ranges of climatic parameters such as rainfall, annual temperature, relative humidity and wind. Speed (Kindersley, 1999).

Table 1. Some physical and chemical properties of the soil of the experimental site

/ No	Depth (cm)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	T.C	ρ	pH		EC(dsm ⁻¹ (25°C))	O.M.	T.N.	Exchangable Cation(cmolKg ⁻¹)				C.E.C
							H ₂ O	CaCl ₂				Na	K	Ca	Mg	
1	0-15	38	44	18	Loam	1.43	5.60	4.80	0.08	0.079	0.120	0.35	0.15	1.8	0.43	4.8
	15-30	38	38	24	Loam	1.68										
	30-45	42	34	24	Loam	1.43										
	45-60	40	39	22	Loam	1.42										
2	0-15	36	44	20	Loam	1.37	5.8	4.70	0.07	0.400	0.240	0.64	0.36	2.5	0.59	6.2
	15-30	36	38	26	Loam	1.59										
	30-45	36	36	28	Loam	1.49										
	45-60	31	38	30	Loam	1.47										
3	0-15	34	36	30	Clay-Loam	1.54	5.4	4.30	0.05	0.460	0.240	0.44	0.32	2.5	1.25	6.8
	15-30	36	42	22	Loam	1.68										
	30-45	42	34	24	Loam	1.64										
	45-60	41	36	25	Loam	1.54										
4	0-15	38	44	18	Loam	1.47	5.9	3.90	0.08	0.320	0.240	0.46	0.26	2.2	0.69	5.6
	15-30	34	44	22	Loam	1.67										
	30-45	44	30	26	Loam	1.68										
	45-60	43	44	18	Loam	1.47										
5	0-15	32	50	18	Silty-Loam	1.40	5.5	4.20	0.07	0.140	0.183	0.57	0.20	2.5	0.69	6.2
	15-30	46	18	36	Loam	1.52										
	30-45	36	38	32	Loam	1.63										
	45-60	40	37	33	Sandy-Loam Clay-Loam Clay-Loam	1.62										

Key: TC = Textural class; ρ = Mean bulk density(gcm⁻¹); EC=Electrical conductivity; OM= Organic matter content(%); TM=Total nitrogen(%)
C.E.C= cation exchange capacity.

Table 2: Effects of varieties and irrigation scheduling on growth and yield components of Irish potatoes

Treatments	Growth Components				Yield Components						
	Days to % germination	50 Days to 50 % flowering	Days to 50 tuberisation	%	Total yields (t/ha)	Yields(t/ha) at some sizes ranges(mm)				Number of tubers	Mean tuber weight (g)
						T<25.4	25.4≤ T<50.8	50.8≤ T<72.6	72.6≤ T<101.6		
Varities											
Pakistan	18.17b	63.43b	43.83b		3.48	0.18	1.49c	1.43a	0.49a	171.33	29
Nicola	18.33b	NF	48.43b		3.78	0.22	2.56b	0.98b	0.27b	173.00	34
SP	23.67a	70.42a	49.58a		3.32	0.17	2.19b	0.89b	0.04b	195.42	25
Dual	17.12b	NF	42.58b		4.54	0.24	3.15a	1.17b	0.01b	221.42	35
Significance	**	**	*		NS	NS	*	**	*	NS	NS
L.S.D.5%	99.5	99.1	95.8		--	--	95.9	99.4	95.5	--	--
Irrigation Schedules											
CPE 20mm	NE	NE	48.45		4.89	0.22	2.24	1.53a	0.33	203.92	34
CPE 30mm	NE	NE	46.75		3.73	0.21	2.17	1.16b	0.26	198.00	32.08
CPE 40mm	NE	NE	46.75		3.50	0.19	2.45	0.91b	0.14	186.50	31.25
fixed 7-days	NE	NE	46.75		3.49	0.19	2.54	0.79b	0.09	181.75	28.33
Significance	--	--	NS		NS	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	NS
L.S.D.5%	--	--	--		--	--	--	99.1	--	--	--

a. All means within a column followed by the same letter are not different at 5% level of significance using LSD

b. NS=Not significant. NF=Non-flowering variety. NE= No effect.

c. T=Potato tubers

Table 3: Effects of varieties and irrigation scheduling on irrigation variables, crop water use and crop water use efficiency.

Treatments	Irrigation Events	Irrigation interval (days)	Depth of water (mm)	Volume of water used (m ³)	Crop water use (mm)	Crop water use efficiency (t/ha-mm)
Varieties						
Pakistan	-	-	-	-	399.32	71.79
Nicola	-	-	-	-	399.33	9.15
SP	-	-	-	-	409.55	9.95
Dual	-	-	-	-	388.52	10.93
Significance	-	-	-	-	NS	NS
LSD at 5%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Irrigation Scheduling						
CPE 20 mm	18 a	3.18b	900 a	243.0 a	551.0 a	48.85 a
CPE 30 mm	16 b	3.80 b	800 b	216.0 b	420.0 b	18.36 b
CPE 40 mm	15 b	4.67 b	700 b	202.5 b	341.2 b	12.85 b
Fixed 7-days	12 b	7.00 a	600 b	162.0 b	289.28 b	15.85 b
Significance	**	*	**	**	*	**
LSD at 5%	99.4	95.3	99.7	97.7	95.1	99.5

a. All means within a column followed by same letters are not different at 5 % level of significance using LSD.

b. NS=Not significant.

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